

NFDI4Objects
National Digital Information Infrastructure
Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data

Von der Hosentasche
in den Wissensgraph?

Smartphone-3D als FAIR Digital Object in der SquirrelBase

Florian Thiery M.Sc.

3D Tage | 2026 | 25-26 Feb 2026 | Dresden | Germany | 26/02/2026

Themenblock: AG3D

Florian Thierry CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALLE

via <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Mit Linked Open Data (LOD) ermöglichen wir Verlinkung von (Meta)Daten und *binären* Messdaten und die Basis zu **FAIRification**

Ziel ist das **Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem**

GeoSPARQL

CIDOC CRM

CFF

DCAT

LOD

Wikibase

FAIR Digital Object

Data

Metadata

PID

Hierzu ist ein *Mix* von **Linked Open Data** (RDF), **Wikibase** Instanzen, und **FAIR Digital Objects** (FDO) sinnvoll

LOD

Wikibase

FDO

GIS

OSM

LPG

HIN

EpiDoc

Aber wie “füttern” wir das **Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem**?

FAIR Digital Object

A Squirrel Implementation

FAIR Digital Object

Data

Metadata

PID

FAIR Digital Object - **Squirrel Implementation**

Florian Thierry CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

FAIR Digital Object - Squirrel Implementation - **MD.cff**

via <https://citation-file-format.github.io/>

Citation File Format (CFF)

About

Events

Documentation

Tutorials

Create CFF file

4 minute read

What is a CITATION.cff file?

CITATION.cff files are plain text files with human- and machine-readable citation information for software (and datasets). Code developers can include them in their repositories to let others know how to correctly cite their software.

This is an example of a simple CITATION.cff file:

```

cff-version: 1.2.0
message: "If you use this software, please cite it as below."
authors:
  - family-names: Druskat
    given-names: Stephan
    orcid: https://orcid.org/1234-5678-9101-1121
title: "My Research Software"
version: 2.0.4
identifiers:
  - type: doi
    value: 10.5281/zenodo.1234
date-released: 2021-08-11
  
```

The format of CITATION.cff files is the **Citation File Format (CFF)**.

ON THIS PAGE

WHAT IS A CITATION.CFF FILE?

WHY YOU SHOULD ADD A CITATION.CFF FILE TO YOUR REPOSITORY!

SUPPORTED BY GITHUB

SUPPORTED BY ZENODO

SUPPORTED BY ZOTERO

CREATE A CITATION.CFF FILE NOW!

TOOLS FOR WORKING WITH CITATION.CFF FILES

HAVE AN IDEA? FOUND A PROBLEM?

FAIR Digital Object - Squirrel Implementation - **CITATION.cff**

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oVQIH>

CIIC 81 - MD.cff

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oVQIH>

CIIC 81 - CITATION.cff

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CIIC 81 - Files and Roles

CIIC 81 - FDO Overview

via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635>

```
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> a dcat:Dataset, crm:di:DI, crm:E73, fdo:3DDataFDO ;
dct:description "Ogham Stone C0074-148---- located in the UCC Stone Corridor" ;
dct:hasVersion "1.0" ;
dct:creator <urn:fdo-squirrel:person/1ef85dc7cadee6db> ;
dct:creator <urn:fdo-squirrel:person/8e916ce55425de21> ;
dct:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> ;
dct:publisher <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q73901970> ;
dct:title "C0074-148----" ;
dcat:distribution <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/c2585e6ac0ee17a4>, <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/8d9eb2eb0b8db609>, ... ;
dct:created "2024-06-05"^^xsd:date ;
dct:issued "2024-06-05"^^xsd:date ;
dct:modified "2026-02-21"^^xsd:date ;
schema:funding "Community Project" ;
dct:spatial <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/11071361392> ;
schema:latitude "51.893715"^^xsd:decimal ;
schema:longitude "-8.4924208"^^xsd:decimal ;
fdo:context "Ogham Stones in the Wild and in Museums in Ireland bearing Ogham inscriptions." ;
dct:type <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q02016147> ;
dct:subject <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22731> ;
dct:description "make 3d model available" ;
dct:description "good" ;
dct:description "low" ;
dct:provenance "{ "software": "KIRI Engine", "steps": "Take photos, align photos; build dense cloud; generate mesh; texture; export." }
```

```
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> geosparql:hasGeometry <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_geom> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_geom> a sf:Point .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_geom> geosparql:asWKT "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-8.4924208 51.8937150)"^^geosparql:wktLiteral .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> dct:temporal <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_temporal> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_temporal> a dct:PeriodOfTime .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_temporal> owl:sameAs <http://chronontology.dainst.org/period/aChcHzd1Bhkt> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_temporal> rdfs:label "Ogham stone inscriptions (ca. 4th–7th century CE)" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_temporal> dcat:startDate "300"^^xsd:integer .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635_temporal> dcat:endDate "699"^^xsd:integer .
```

```
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> cff:keywords "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> cff:keywords "UCC Stone Corridor" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> cff:license "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> cff:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> cff:license-url "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> cff:license-url <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> codemeta:keywords "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> codemeta:keywords "UCC Stone Corridor" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> codemeta:license "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> codemeta:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> dcat:keyword "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> dcat:keyword "UCC Stone Corridor" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> dct:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> dct:subject "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> dct:subject "UCC Stone Corridor" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> schema:description "Ogham Stone C0074-148---- located in the UCC Stone Corridor" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> schema:keywords "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> schema:keywords "UCC Stone Corridor" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> schema:license "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> schema:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> wdt:P275 "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> wdt:P275 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> wdt:P921 "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635> wdt:P921 "UCC Stone Corridor" .

<https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html> rdfs:label "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0" .
```


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via <https://skfb.ly/6V0IiH>

CIIC 81 - FDO-RDF pt. I

```

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/725646e0ce112e> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/CITATION.cff ;
dcat:byteSize 326 ;
dcat:mediaType "text/yaml" ;
fdo:path "CITATION.cff" ;
fdo:role "metadata" ;
fdo:sha256 "c2838e4c0e17a4cce6e39e75a9a4b3a17a49c0d270eaa2a862cb503017e5"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/d9db2eb088d609> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/C0074-148----.glib ;
dcat:byteSize 126317064 ;
dcat:mediaType "model/gltf-binary" ;
fdo:path "C0074-148----.glib" ;
fdo:role "model" ;
fdo:sha256 "8d9ebcb8bb60949c014957127586c6ce735d1718f33ed175e2b45ecaef16"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/029be5cdd4702fd> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/C0074-148----.jpg ;
dcat:byteSize 1311939 ;
dcat:mediaType "image/jpeg" ;
fdo:path "C0074-148----.jpg" ;
fdo:role "documentation" ;
fdo:sha256 "029be5cdd4702fd70f4119a36a574498da992fd4747d53ac5484e4c99005627"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/33c3189610daa87e> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/C0074-148----.msx ;
dcat:byteSize 6757286 ;
dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
fdo:path "C0074-148----.msx" ;
fdo:role "model" ;
fdo:sha256 "33c3189610daa87e03f94b63323ae6bb4e5e8a419cb5c857aa0df79e5d0ba08"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/1b1cc5a60e2194e9> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/C0074-148----.msx ;
dcat:byteSize 15864576 ;
dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
fdo:path "C0074-148----.msx" ;
fdo:role "model" ;
fdo:sha256 "1b1cc5a60e2194e98b63e647a9a67cae43c77d50ac49ff5840cb12a9113a85"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/23acc58da43af2b> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/C0074-148----.ply ;
dcat:byteSize 84070110 ;
dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
fdo:path "C0074-148----.ply" ;
fdo:role "model" ;
fdo:sha256 "23acc58da43af28f0216ef346d643df67bca10786ba7007b091a375cc150f"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/eb8d117bfd2302a> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/fdo-metadata.ttl ;
dcat:byteSize 11096 ;
dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
fdo:path "fdo-metadata.ttl" ;
fdo:role "data" ;
fdo:sha256 "eb8d117bfd2302a588b0e5e252cf24f3ce874c84c3f205a0e4f2c13f0d8b99"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/db118180b9ee910d> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/MD.cff ;
dcat:byteSize 230 ;
dcat:mediaType "text/yaml" ;
fdo:path "MD.cff" ;
fdo:role "metadata" ;
fdo:sha256 "db118180b9ee910df0929ac0512677096e10273e96cca1f04918ac7e77a5097d"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/3ffdb3e5f0a032b> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/rdf_modelling_report.html ;
dcat:byteSize 17757 ;
dcat:mediaType "text/html" ;
fdo:path "rdf_modelling_report.html" ;
fdo:role "data" ;
fdo:sha256 "3ffdb3e5f0a032b717b7f1a2dff0f37c8171d5ea3d3c913245bbff132f9"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/f64d3aff39e6eb> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/rdf_modelling_report.json ;
dcat:byteSize 14611 ;
dcat:mediaType "application/json" ;
fdo:path "rdf_modelling_report.json" ;
fdo:role "documentation" ;
fdo:sha256 "f64d3aff39e6eb327bcc9cb6e89a4a14682eab888d9c7d48d5e793726dc55"

urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/64b639f42b38d2f> a dcat:Distribution, crm:dig:D9 ;
dcat:accessURL urn:fdo-squirrel:content/Texture_Ortho.jpg ;
dcat:byteSize 2397100 ;
dcat:mediaType "image/jpeg" ;
fdo:path "Texture_Ortho.jpg" ;
fdo:role "documentation" ;
fdo:sha256 "64b639f42b38d2f3148c897e8a047bb4451102e122af02a75d09088e0c120a"

```

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CIIC 81 - FDO-RDF pt. II

SquirrelBase

A Squirrel Knowledge Base for 3D Models

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

<https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud>

via <https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q22>

Item **Discussion**

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Crate
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148---- (Q48)

No description defined

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148----	No description defined	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
default for all languages	No label defined	--	

Statements

instance of	Object
	0 references

Wikidata Q-ID	Q13052981
	0 references

OSM ID	node/11071361392
	0 references

representative point	51°53'37.3740"N, 8°29'32.7149"W
	0 references

via <https://tjp.de/Oale3>

item	itemLabel	geo
Q23	Adlerstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Point(6.0187331 50.7617299)
Q4	Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Kuddamm)	Point(13.3249878 52.5026745)
Q25	Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande)	Point(6.0187331 50.7617299)
Q6	Rom Capitol Kopf Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906)
Q7	Rom Capitol Hand Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906111)
Q8	Rom Capitol Fuß Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906111)
Q29	Berliner Siegestraße (Mosaik)	Point(13.300108 52.514512)
Q10	Der "Große Sitzender" (Dom Würzburg)	Point(9.9318653 49.7936363)
Q11	Gedenkstein von Kurfürst Karl (Schloss Heidelberg)	Point(8.714044 49.410568)
Q12	Vater Rhein (Schloss Heidelberg)	Point(8.7191369 49.4102478)
Q13	Domnagel (Speyer)	Point(8.441199 49.317267)
Q14	Geißbockbrunnen (Deidesheim)	Point(8.190597 49.407566)
Q15	Köln Hohenzollernbrücke (Schlosser)	Point(6.965944 50.941421)
Q16	Statua del Mendicante di Anterselva	Point(12.1679203 46.6825371)
Q22	Milestone Maudlin Street (Kilkenny)	Point(-7.2442662 52.6525992)
Q23	CIIC 153	Point(9.6430769 52.2786257)

Die Squirrel Base stellt FAIRe Metadaten für 3D Objekte bereit

SquirrelBase - Identifier & Metadata

SquirrelBase - 3D Data & FDO

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oVOIH>

CIIC 81 - Identifier & Metadata

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/ovQIh>

CIIC 81 - 3D Data & FDO

Item **Discussion**

CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148---- (Q48)

No description defined

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148----	No description defined
German	No label defined	No description defined
American English	No label defined	No description defined
default for all languages	No label defined	—

Statements

instance of	Q48	Object	▼ 0 references
Wikidata Q-ID	Q48	Q130529871	▼ 0 references
OSM ID	Q48	node/11071361392	▼ 0 references
representative point	Q48	51°53′37.3740″N, 8°29′32.7149″W	▼ 0 references

aligned with term

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>

alignment label	Ogham Stone
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	FDO

▼ 0 references

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121592049>

alignment label	UCC Stone Corridor
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	exhibition
alignment source	FDO

▼ 0 references

CIIC 81 - SquirrelBase I

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

3DHOP URL

<http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CO074-148---->

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	iPhone
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Anne-Karoline Distel
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

Sketchfab URL

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/cork-ogham-stone-ciic-81-ucc-4-4cb26986be274ee099515c2baa3b1825>

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	iPhone
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Anne-Karoline Distel
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

CIIC 81 - SquirrelBase II

FDO URL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635>

FDO type	fdo:3DDataFDO
FDO format	glb
	ply
	nxs
	nxz
FDO license	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0
FDO release version	v0.3.1

▼ 0 references

CIIC 81 - SquirrelBase III

CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148----

Item:Q48 · squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud · 2026-02-23

Statements

instance of P1	Object Q2
Wikidata Q-ID P6	Q130529871 Q130529871
OSM ID P7	node/11071361392
representative point P8	<p>51°53'37.374"N, 8°29'32.7149"W Point(-8.4924208 51.893715)</p>
aligned with term P11	<p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147 alignment label P27 Ogham Stone alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:exactMatch Q33 exactMatch alignment score P14 7 Star Q37 ★★★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 object type alignment source P16 FDO</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121592049 alignment label P27 UCC Stone Corridor alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:relatedMatch Q35 relatedMatch alignment score P14 3 Star Q41 ★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 exhibition alignment source P16 FDO</p>
3DHOP URL P3	<p>http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CO074-148--- acquisition method P28 Structure from Motion (SfM) Q45 acquisition hardware P29 iPhone acquisition software P19 KIRI engine acquisition creator P20 Anne-Karoline Distel acquisition license P21 CC BY-NC-SA 4.0</p>
Sketchfab URL P5	<p>https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/cork-ogham-stone-ciic-81-ucc-4-4cb26986be274ee099515c2baa3b1825 acquisition method P28 Structure from Motion (SfM) Q45 acquisition hardware P29 iPhone acquisition software P19 KIRI engine acquisition creator P20 Anne-Karoline Distel acquisition license P21 CC BY-NC-SA 4.0</p>
FDO URL P9	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635 FDO type P2a fdo:3DDataFDO FDO format P23 glb FDO license P24 CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 FDO release version P25 v0.3.1</p>

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CIIC 81 - Wikibase Schema

Semantic Alignment

A Squirrel semantic alignment approach

The property `skos:relatedMatch` is used to state an **associative mapping link between two concepts**.

The property `skos:closeMatch` is used to link two concepts that are **sufficiently similar** that they can be used interchangeably in some information retrieval applications. In order to avoid the possibility of "compound errors" when combining mappings across more than two concept schemes, `skos:closeMatch` is not declared to be a transitive property.

The property `skos:exactMatch` is used to link two concepts, indicating a high degree of confidence that the **concepts can be used interchangeably** across a wide range of information retrieval applications. `skos:exactMatch` is a transitive property, and is a sub-property of `skos:closeMatch`.

via <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/#mapping>

SKOS Mapping Properties - related/close/exact match

Idee eines **7 Star Alignment Model** (auf Basis von SKOS)

Perceptions of Probability

via <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/zonation-perceptions>

Perceptions of Probability (by Zoni Nation)

Perceptions of Probability (auf Basis von SKOS)

aligned with term

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oVOIH>

	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147
alignment label	Ogham Stone
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	FDO

▼ 0 references

	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121592049
alignment label	UCC Stone Corridor
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	exhibition
alignment source	FDO

▼ 0 references

«Property P11» AlignedWithTerm
+url: URL +alignment_label P27: String +alignment_type_skos P12: Item Q33-EM Q34-CM Q35-RM +alignment_score P14: Item Q37..Q43 +alignment_repository P13: String +alignment_description P15: String +alignment_source P16: String

CIIC 81 - SquirrelBase Alignment

Beispiele

Genug der Theorie ...

Antholzer See: “Steinmännchen”

Antholzer See: "Steinmännchen"

Item:Q60 - squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud - 2026-02-22

Statements

instance of P1	temporal Object Q17
representative point P8	46°53'18.1032"N, 12°10'11.568"E Point(12.16989 46.888362)
aligned with term P11	<p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q7321974</p> <p>alignment label P27 Steinmännchen alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:exactMatch Q233 exactMatch alignment score P14 7 Star Q27 ★★★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 object type alignment source P16 survey</p> <p>https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300006960</p> <p>alignment label P27 cairns alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:exactMatch Q233 exactMatch alignment score P14 7 Star Q27 ★★★★★ alignment repository P13 Getty AAT alignment description P15 object type alignment source P16 survey</p> <p>https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/14599988</p> <p>alignment label P27 Antholzer See alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:relatedMatch Q35 relatedMatch alignment score P14 3 Star Q11 ★★★ alignment repository P13 OSM alignment description P15 temporal site alignment source P16 survey</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q572562</p> <p>alignment label P27 Antholzer See alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:relatedMatch Q35 relatedMatch alignment score P14 3 Star Q11 ★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 temporal site alignment source P16 survey</p>
KIRI URL P4	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/shareModel/7a02d4f6285a42a6abb1803a1e1492a5 acquisition method P18 Structure From Motion (SfM) Q45 acquisition hardware P20 Samsung Galaxy S22 acquisition software P19 KIRI engine acquisition creator P20 Florian Thiery acquisition license P21 CC BY 4.0
FDO URL P9	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18732892 FDO type P22 fdo:3DDataFDO FDO format P23 glb FDO license P24 CC BY 4.0 FDO release version P25 v0.2

Core Metadata

Object: Steinmännchen (wd:Q7321974)
Material: Stone (wd:Q22731)
Keywords: Antholzer See
Created: 2026-01-03
Creator: Thiery, Florian
Publisher: Research Squirrel Engineers Network
Condition: good · Urgency: low
Spatial: OSM Relation 14599988
lat: 46.888362 · lon: 12.16988
Temporal: ChronOntology dfwAgTD5WMEV
start: 2026 · end: 2026
Technique: KIRI Engine (Photogrammetry)

FDO: Steinmännchen / Antholzer See 03.01.2026
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18732892
64 files · CC-BY-4.0 · v1.0

fdo:role = model
model/gltf-binary
(1 file)

fdo:role = metadata
CITATION.cff
MD.cff
(2 files)

fdo:role = documentation
image/jpeg
(61 files)

Antholzer See: Steinmännchen - FDO

Kopisch, A., Thariet, E., & Wiegmann, U. (2018).
De Heizemänncher von Kölle (1. Auflage). NordSüd. p.7.

Heinz Lektor von Druck

Heinz Gast

Heinz Kreativ

Heinz Klein

Heinz Mann

Heinz Keule

Heinz Dandy

Heinz Köbes
Gibt es auch in
Midi

Heinz Eau
Das Original hängt in der Glockengasse in
einem der Bögen des 4711 Hauses.

basemap: ESRI Topografie: Tiles © Esri — Esri, DeLorme, NAVTEQ, TomTom, Intermap, iPC, USGS, FAO, NPS, NRCAN, GeoBase, Kadaster NL, Ordnance Survey, Esri Japan, METI, Esri China (Hong Kong), and the GIS User Community
data: https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/viewer?mid=1fs7A5eHvXh-U4eiVSpPobQaD0fE_1Su

De Heizemänncher von Kölle

Köln: Heinzelmännchen "Heinz Eau"

Statements

instance of P1	Object Q2
Wikidata Q-ID P6	Q138425201 Q138425201
OSM ID P7	node/12848270361
representative point P8	50°56'18.2299"N, 6°57'8.2422"E Point(6.9522895; 50.9383972)
aligned with term P11	<p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q537513</p> <p>alignment label P27 Heinzelmännchen alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:exactMatch Q33 exactMatch alignment score P14 7 Star Q37 ★★★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 object type alignment source P16 survey</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q138425168</p> <p>alignment label P27 Kölner Heinzelmännchen Weg alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:relatedMatch Q35 relatedMatch alignment score P14 3 Star Q41 ★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 part of way alignment source P16 Website</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q33056801</p> <p>alignment label P27 Die Heinzelmännchen (Gedicht von August Kopisch) alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:relatedMatch Q35 relatedMatch alignment score P14 3 Star Q41 ★★★ alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 mentioned in a poem alignment source P16 Website</p>
KIRI URL P4	<p>https://www.kiriengine.app/share/shareModel/2ec352e62fa14453b1dd07d7d965aefc</p> <p>acquisition method P18 Structure from Motion (SfM) Q45 acquisition hardware P29 Samsung Galaxy S22 acquisition software P19 KIRI engine acquisition creator P20 Florian Thiery acquisition license P21 CC BY 4.0</p>
FDO URL P9	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18740523</p> <p>FDO type P22 fdo:3DDataFDO FDO format P23 glb FDO license P24 CC BY 4.0 FDO release version P25 v0.3</p>

Core Metadata

- Object: Heinzelmännchen (wd:Q537513)
- Material: Bronze (wd:Q34095)
- Keywords: Die Heinz Welt
- Created: 2025-07-25
- Creator: Thiery, Florian
- Publisher: Research Squirrel Engineers Network
- Condition: good · Urgency: low
- Spatial: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/12848270361>
- lat: 50.9383972 · lon: 6.9522895
- Temporal: ChronOntology dfwAgTD5WMEV
- start: 2026 · end: 2026
- Technique: KIRI Engine (Photogrammetry)

FDO: Kunstwerk "Heinz Eau" (Köln)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18740523

32 files · CC-BY-4.0 · v1.0

fdo:role = model

model/gltf-binary
(2 files)

fdo:role = metadata

CITATION.cff
MD.cff
(2 files)

fdo:role = documentation

image/jpeg
(28 files)

Buddy Bears

Galerie Diskussion

• **Deutsch:** Die **Buddy Bears** (auch **Buddy Bears**) sind ein Kunstprojekt mit vielen bunten Bären Plastiken in ganz Berlin. Die Bären gibt es in den Grundrissformen stehend, sitzend, auf allen vier Beinen, handend, handierend machend. Sie sind sowohl als Kommunikationseinrichtungen als auch von Firmen oder Privatpersonen erworben worden und individuell gestaltet.

• **Englisch:** The **Buddy Bears** are an art project with many individually painted bear statues throughout Berlin, Germany. There is an *interactive map* showing all Buddy Bears.

In Berlin

Berlin-Charlottenburg

Berlin-Grünwald

User:BlueFISH.as, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

maps via <https://www.buddy-bear.com/en/individual-buddy-bears/buddy-bear-worldmap>

Buddy Bears (hier in Berlin)

Berlin: “Charlotten-Bär” #948 von Nana Topchishvili

Berlin: “Charlotten-Bär” von Nana Topchishvili

Item:Q52 · squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud · 2026-02-23

Statements

instance of P1	Object Q2
OSM ID P7	node/6743185324
Wikidata Q-ID P6	Q138426731 <small>Q138426731</small>
representative point P8	52°31'1.1186"N, 13°18'28.7903"E Point(13.3079973 52.5169774) <div style="display: inline-block; width: 100px; height: 100px; margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
aligned with term P11	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q152445 alignment label P27 Buddy Bär alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:exactMatch Q33 <small>exactMatch</small> alignment score P14 7 Star Q37 <small>*****</small> alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 object type alignment source P16 survey
	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q138426946 alignment label P27 Nana Topchishvili alignment type (SKOS) P12 skos:relatedMatch Q35 <small>relatedMatch</small> alignment score P14 4 Star Q40 <small>****</small> alignment repository P13 Wikidata alignment description P15 creator alignment source P16 Website
KIRI URL P4	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/shareModel/dbbdb4db9ac54bb8a3b17503deedd761 acquisition method P18 Structure from Motion (SfM) Q45 acquisition hardware P29 Samsung Galaxy S22 acquisition software P19 KIRI engine acquisition creator P20 Florian Thiery acquisition license P21 CC BY 4.0
FDO URL P9	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18742669 FDO type P22 fdo:3DDataFDO FDO format P23 obj FDO license P24 CC BY 4.0 FDO release version P25 v0.3

Core Metadata

- Object: Buddy Bär (wd:Q152445)
- Material: fiberglass (wd:Q7224880)
- Keywords: Buddy Bär
- Created: 2025-05-29
- Creator: Thiery, Florian
- Publisher: Research Squirrel Engineers Network
- Condition: good · Urgency: low
- Spatial: OSM node/6743185324
lat: 52.5169774 · lon: 13.3079973
- Temporal: ChronOntology
dfwAgTD5WMEV
start: 2026 · end: 2026
- Technique: KIRI Engine (Photogrammetry)

Berlin: Charlotten-Bär - FDO

maps via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/4629093> © OpenStreetMap Mitwirkende

Dguendel, CC BY 3.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Kassel_7000_Eichen.jpg)

“7000 Eichen” in Kassel (Joseph Beuys, 1982 / documenta 7)

Kassel: Beuys-Steile B 1036, Kunstprojekt "7000 Eichen"

Kassel: Beuys-Stele B 1036 "7000 Eichen"

Item:Q56 · squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud · 2026-02-23

Statements

instance of P1	Object Q2
OSM ID P7	node/3647679932
representative point P8	51°18'47.2471"N, 9°29'53.569°E Point(9.4982136 51.3131242)
aligned with term P11	<p>https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/4629093</p> <p>alignment label P27: 7000 Eichen alignment type (SKOS) P12: skos:closeMatch Q34 closeMatch alignment score P14: 6 Star Q38 ***** alignment repository P13: OSM alignment description P15: art project alignment source P16: Literature</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q261274</p> <p>alignment label P27: 7000 Eichen alignment type (SKOS) P12: skos:closeMatch Q34 closeMatch alignment score P14: 6 Star Q38 ***** alignment repository P13: Wikidata alignment description P15: art project alignment source P16: Literature</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q138426902</p> <p>alignment label P27: Beuys Basalstele alignment type (SKOS) P12: skos:exactMatch Q33 exactMatch alignment score P14: 7 Star Q37 ***** alignment repository P13: Wikidata alignment description P15: object type alignment source P16: survey</p> <p>http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q153965</p> <p>alignment label P27: Joseph Beuys alignment type (SKOS) P12: skos:relatedMatch Q25 relatedMatch alignment score P14: 4 Star Q40 ***** alignment repository P13: Wikidata alignment description P15: artist alignment source P16: Literature</p>
KIRI URL P4	<p>https://www.kiriengine.app/share/shareModel/d7b9f6c900b47449d38453c06513a1f</p> <p>acquisition method P18: Structure from Motion (SDM) Q45 acquisition hardware P29: Samsung Galaxy S22 acquisition software P19: KIRI engine acquisition creator P20: Florian Thiery acquisition license P21: CC BY 4.0</p>
FDO URL P9	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18742693</p> <p>FDO type P22: fdo:3DDataFDO FDO format P23: obj FDO license P24: CC BY 4.0 FDO release version P25: v0.3</p>

Core Metadata

- Object: 7000 Eichen (<https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/4629093>)
- Material: basalt (wd:Q43338)
- Keywords: 7000 Eichen
- Created: 2025-07-14
- Creator: Thiery, Florian
- Publisher: Research Squirrel Engineers Network
- Condition: good · Urgency: low
- Spatial: OSM node/3647679932
lat: 51.3131242 · lon: 9.4982136
- Temporal: ChronOntology dfwAgTD5WMEV
start: 1982 · end: 1982
- Technique: KIRI Engine (Photogrammetry)

Kassel: Beuys-Stele - FDO

Noch mehr Beispiele

Die Liste ist wohl endlos ...

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Graz: "Das Erforschen der Dauer" von Manfred Erjautz

Strudelkopfsattel: Kriegerdenkmal WW I

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Kassel: Dackelgrab zum Andenken an "Erdmann"

Berlin: Briefkasten in der Mommsenstraße

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Köln: Kastell Divitia Deutz “Taktiles Modell”

Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Prager Wildsee: “Eismännchen”

Pragser Wildsee: Eismännchen auf Stein

Finis! Thx!

Questions?

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